

The Influence of Breakfast Habits on Students' Learning Activities Class X SMAN 5 Palu

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ABSTRACT: This study aims to determine how much influence the habit of breakfast has on the learning activities of class X students of SMAN 5 Palu and to determine the impact experienced by class X students of SMAN 5 Palu when they do not make a habit of breakfast before learning activities. This type of research is quantitative research. This research includes descriptive research. Sampling of the research conducted is by taking 25% of the total population (306 people) which is 76 people. Sampling is done by randomly selecting students who will be studied. The method used is descriptive correlational analysis with the formula $P = F / N \times 100\%$, then continued using the *product moment* formula. Data collection in this study is by using a questionnaire. The results of the study obtained data that there is a moderate or sufficient positive influence between breakfast on learning activities of class X students of SMAN 5 Palu with a *product moment* correlation index number of 0.431. While the level of influence obtained from breakfast with learning activities is 18.58%. The impact experienced by students when not doing breakfast is that it can cause a physiological decline in the body, which is characterized by a decrease in blood glucose levels which is the main source.

KEYWORDS: Breakfast, Habits, Learning Activities, Learners.

INTRODUCTION

SMAN 5 Palu is one of the state senior high schools in Central Sulawesi Province, Indonesia. Similar to high school in general in Indonesia, the education period at SMAN 5 Palu is taken within three years of study, starting from class X to class XII. Some students of class X SMAN 5 Palu do learning activities at school without having breakfast first, thus making students less enthusiastic in participating in the learning process. When learning takes place, students are no longer focused due to hunger that interferes. This makes students unable to do good learning activities at school.

Breakfast is very important for everyone to start all their activities throughout the day. Breakfast is an eating and drinking activity carried out since waking up in the morning until 9:00 which aims to fulfill 15-30% of daily nutrient intake (Hardiansyah, 2012). Breakfast is able to meet the needs of energy and nutrients, especially carbohydrates, which are used by the body to increase blood sugar levels. Normal blood sugar levels function to optimize a person's concentration level to be better so that it has a positive impact on productivity (Mughtar, et al, 2011).

Breakfast habits for school children can improve children's cognitive intelligence compared to children who are not accustomed to breakfast (Verdiana & Muniroh, 2017). Breakfast should be a habit because it can affect learning improvement related to children's behavior at school, cognitive abilities, and learning concentration (Iqbal, 2015). Breakfast is very important for the body because it can help fulfill the nutrients needed by the body, maintain endurance, maintain the strength of body stamina, help concentration, good coordination for all senses, and reduce fatigue during activities (Tilong, 2012).

Learning activity is the activeness of students in learning activities to construct their own knowledge. Learners are active in building an understanding of the problems and everything they face in the learning process (Dimiyati & Mudjiono, 2010).

Learning activities are activities that are physical and mental, namely doing and thinking as a series that cannot be separated (Sadirman, 2014). Good learning activity is a condition where students actively involve themselves in managing and responding to various information conveyed by the teacher during learning. Learners who are active during learning can be seen in the following activities: doing assignment reports, listening to other people's opinions, discussing, helping friends who are having difficulty and others (Susanto & Ahmad, 2013).

Learning activities become disrupted and difficult to do due to many factors, one of which is hunger. This symptom usually occurs in students or children who do not eat breakfast before going to school. Underestimating the morning meal will have a very bad effect on the condition of children when carrying out their obligations at school. Lack of energy due to not having breakfast has

the effect of decreasing focus while learning. This is due to the absence of glucose intake in the morning as a source of energy for children. The last time the body gets food intake is only at dinner, while the time between the two is quite far (Sufrin, 2018)

During the learning process, some learners who did not have breakfast were no longer focused on learning but began to feel restless due to hunger. Learning activities are finally disrupted because they only think and wonder when this learning time ends and the break time arrives, so they can no longer follow the learning properly. The problems described above are the background of the influence of breakfast habits on students' learning activities so that this study takes the title of "The Effect of Breakfast Habits on Learning Activities of Class X Students of SMAN 5 Palu". The results of this study are expected to be able to contribute to enriching knowledge about the world of education.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This research is quantitative research. This research includes descriptive research. Descriptive research is research that seeks to describe a symptom, event or incident that occurs to then be described as it is. This study aims to determine the effect of breakfast habits on learning activities of class X students of SMAN 5 Palu.

Sampling of the research conducted is by taking 25% of the total population (306 people), namely 76 people. Sampling is done by random means, namely randomly selecting students to be studied. The questionnaire used is a closed questionnaire, namely a number of lists of questions whose answers have been provided by the author. This questionnaire is given to students who will be studied, the respondent only needs to choose the answer that suits himself. The research instrument used is in the form of a non-test, namely a questionnaire. This questionnaire was submitted to students who were used to obtain information about the effect of breakfast habits on learning activities of class X students of SMAN 5 Palu. This research was conducted for 3 days on November 14, 15 and 18, 2024. To process the data collected in this study, the authors took the following steps:

1. Editing

Checking the list of questions that have been filled in and returned by students of class X SMAN 5 Palu then grouped according to type.

2. Scoring

Scoring is an activity to determine the number of scores, in research using an interval scale (Notoatmodjo, 2010). After going through the editing stage, the author then gave a score to the answers to the questions in the questionnaire. The scoring of each respondent's answer is as follows: Answers with options always given a weight of 3, Answers with options sometimes given a weight of 2 and Answers with options never given a weight of 1.

3. Tabulating

Tabulating is the preparation of data in frequency distribution tables (Notoatmodjo, 2010). Data and answers are presented in tabular form and expressed in frequency and percentage, to determine the percentage, the formula used is: $P = F/N \times 100\%$

Description:

P = Percentage number

F = Frequency of respondents' answers

N = Number of cases (number of frequencies) or number of individuals

100% = Constant number (fixed)

product moment correlation formula from Karl Pearson with the following formula (Syofian, 2013)

$$r_{xy} = \frac{N \cdot \sum XY - \sum X \cdot \sum Y}{\sqrt{\{N \cdot \sum X^2 - (\sum X)^2\} \cdot \{N \cdot \sum Y^2 - (\sum Y)^2\}}}$$

Description:

r_{xy} = Correlation index number "r" product moment

N = Number of cases

$\sum XY$ = Sum of the product of X score and Y score

$\sum X$ = Sum of all X scores

$\sum Y$ = Sum of all scores

Furthermore, to find out how much contribution variable X makes to variable Y, namely by using the coefficient of determination formula; $KD = r^2 \times 100\%$ (Ghozali, 2016).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In testing the hypothesis using product moment correlation technique. The use of this formula is to determine whether there is a significant influence of breakfast habits on the learning activities of class X students of SMAN 5 Palu. The following are the results of the calculation between variable X and variable Y in Table 1 below, then distributed in the product moment correlation formula.

Table 1 Calculation between Variable X and Variable Y

Subject	X	Y	XY	X ²	Y ²
Total	2312	2448	74770	70950	79634
	$\sum X$	$\sum Y$	$\sum XY$	$\sum X^2$	$\sum Y^2$

1. Rough or simple interpretation of data

Based on the above calculations, the correlation number between variable X and variable Y is not negative, which means that between the two variables there is a positive correlation (correlation that goes in the same direction). By paying attention to the value of r_{xy} , namely 0.431, which ranges from 0.40-0.70, it means that the positive correlation between variable X and variable Y is a moderate or sufficient positive correlation.

2. Data interpretation using the "r" value table; $df = N - nr$
 By checking the table of values "r" product moment that by obtaining a df of 74 at a significance level of 5%, $r_t = 0.225$ is obtained, because r_{xy} at a significance level of 5% is greater than r_t ($0.431 > 0.225$) then H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted, which means that at a significance level of 5% there is indeed a significant positive correlation between the X variable and the Y variable. Meanwhile, at the 1% significance level, $r_t = 0.266$ was obtained, because r_{xy} at the 1% significance level is greater than r_t ($0.431 > 0.266$), at the 1% significance level, H_a is accepted and H_0 is rejected, which means that at the 1% significance level there is also a significant positive correlation between the X variable and the Y variable.

To find out how much contribution or contribution is given by variable X to variable Y, we must first know a coefficient called the coefficient of determination or the coefficient of determination with the following formula: $KD = r^2 \times 100\%$
 $= (0,431)^2 \times 100\%$
 $= 0,185761 \times 100\% = 18,58\%$

This research has been conducted at SMAN 5 Palu by collecting data on the influence of breakfast habits on the learning activities of class X students, through the distribution of questionnaires distributed to class X students with alternative answers always, sometimes and never. The number of items in the questionnaire was 26 questions.

SMAN 5 Palu is a school that has learners who are mostly active when learning in class. Class X learners, a small number of them have breakfast before going to school and some buy food at the school canteen if they do not have time to have breakfast at home. Whereas breakfast is a very important thing that must be done by students because with breakfast, the students' bodies will be more fit and fresh besides that students will be more focused when learning.

Based on the results of data analysis that has been done, it shows that the influence of breakfast habits on the learning activities of class X students of SMAN 5 Palu obtained a moderate or sufficient positive correlation by obtaining a value of 0.431. Then by checking the table of the value of "r" product moment obtained ($0.431 > 0.225$) at a significance level of 5% and ($0.431 > 0.266$) at a significance level of 1% then H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted, which means that there is a significant positive influence between variable X and variable Y. With this value it is known that the contribution or contribution given by variable X (breakfast) to variable Y (learning activity) is equal to 18.58%. The coefficient of determination shows that the contribution of variable X is able to explain the variation of variable Y. The coefficient of determination obtained is low which means that the ability of variable X to influence variable Y is 18.58%, while 81.42% is explained by other variables besides variables X and Y in the study.

This is in line with research conducted by Rosalina & Djayusmantoko (2022) showing that there is a significant relationship between breakfast habits and students' learning activities, students with good breakfast habits can do good learning activities as well, on the contrary, if their breakfast habits are not good then their learning activities are not good.

This is also in line with research conducted by Rima, et al (2020) showing that learning activities increase because there is a statistically significant effect of breakfast on learning activities.

The focus of students' learning in the classroom can be seen from the attention of students when the teacher explains the lesson and students can answer questions asked by the teacher after explaining. From the responses given by students, it can be analyzed regarding the effect of students' breakfast habits on learning activities carried out in class.

Factors that affect students' learning activities are classified into two, namely: Internal factors, namely factors that exist within the individual who is learning, including physical factors (health and disability), psychological factors (intelligence, attention, interest, talent, motive, maturity and readiness), and fatigue factors (physical fatigue and spiritual fatigue). External factors, namely factors that exist outside the individual, include family factors (how parents educate, relationships between members, home atmosphere, family economic conditions, understanding of parents and cultural background), school factors (teaching methods, curriculum, teacher relations with students, student relations with students, school discipline, learning tools, school time, lesson standards above the size, building conditions, learning methods and home assignments) and community factors (student activities in society, mass media, friends hanging out and forms of community life).

Based on the questionnaire data, information was obtained that various reasons that often cause students not to have breakfast are because some feel that time is very limited with a long distance from school, waking up late, or there is no appetite for breakfast then some students have parents who are busy working so they do not have time to prepare breakfast.

This can interfere with students' learning focus in the classroom. In addition, breakfast if underestimated can interfere with health, including stomach pain to mag, dizziness and even worse can cause fainting. The impact experienced by learners when not having breakfast is that it can cause a physiological decline in the body, which is characterized by a decrease in glucose levels in the blood which is the main source. This can affect all organs of the body, one of which is the work of the brain, due to a decrease in energy intake to the brain as a result the ability of students to move will be reduced (Ma'arif, et al, 2004).

This study is in line with the theory that learners who skip breakfast are related to brain activity, where the benefits of breakfast are to provide energy to the brain so that memory can improve, minimize the risk of anemia and concentrate when learning. Learners who skip breakfast will experience many problems, including difficulties in problem solving, short-term memory, reasoning, concentration and low work productivity. In addition, learners who skip breakfast will also experience hunger, weakness, dizziness and drowsiness while studying at school (Rosalina & Djayusmantoko, 2022).

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the research and discussion above, it can be concluded that:

1. The results of the study obtained data that there is a moderate or sufficient positive influence between breakfast on the learning activity of class X students of SMAN 5 Palu with a product moment correlation index number 0.431. While the level of influence obtained from breakfast with learning activities is 18.58%.
2. The impact experienced by students when they do not have breakfast is that it can cause a physiological decline in the body, which is characterized by a decrease in glucose levels in the blood which is the main source. This can affect all organs of the body, one of which is the work of the brain, due to a decrease in energy intake to the brain as a result the ability of students to move will be reduced.

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